

Some Transformations of *cis*-Tetrahydrobenzopyran-2-ones : The Precursor Lactones to the Trichothecenes[†]

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Attempted photolytic ethylene addition to lactone **3** affords only the intramolecular cycloadduct **5** and the rearranged product **6**, the latter arising from a photo-ene reaction. Similarly lactone **4** also furnishes the cycloadduct **8** and the ene product **9**. Basic hydrolysis of **6** followed by esterification produces the hydroxydiester **10** which on oxidation furnishes the highly functionalised bicyclo(3.2.1)octane derivative **11**.

The trichothecene family of highly oxygenated sesquiterpenes¹ enclose an unusual oxabicyclo(3.2.1)octane unit in their structural inlay. Trichodermol **1** and verrucarol **2** are the representative members of this group. Their intriguing structural network and associated physiological properties have resulted in one of the most intensive efforts directed at their chemical synthesis². In our own efforts directed towards their synthesis we had previously described³ the synthesis of bicyclic lactones **3** and **4** incorporating the requi-

purification of the product furnished three compounds. The most polar material accounting for about 20% was found to be the recovered lactone **3**. The least polar substance was characterised as the intramolecular cycloaddition product **5** from detailed investigations. Analytical data showed a molecular formula C₁₄H₁₈O₄, the same as the lactone **3**. In the ir it showed absorptions at 1780 and 1725 cm⁻¹, indicating a γ -lactone and ester function respectively. Concrete evi-

site *cis*-ring junction and the double bond in proper position in ring A, which can serve as potential start-off points for the synthesis of **2** and **1**. In this report we describe some interesting chemistry involving these lactones in course of their synthetic transformations⁴.

Results and Discussion

For the transformation of the bicyclic lactone **3** into a tricyclic system comprising the oxabicyclo(3.2.1)octane unit for the ultimate synthesis of **2**, it was proposed to involve rearrangement of a cyclobutylcarbinol system which will arise from photolytic ethylene addition to **3** followed by reduction (Scheme 1). A similar approach involving acetylene addition to a bicyclic unsaturated lactone had been employed by White *et al.*⁵. With this in view a benzene solution of the lactone **3** with added acetone was irradiated for 8 h with continuous bubbling of ethylene. Chromatographic

dence in support of structure **5** was obtained from ¹H nmr spectrum which showed the absence of any olefinic proton and instead showed a six proton singlet for the two methyl groups at δ 1.20 and a downfield multiplet at δ 4.77 for the hydrogen at the ring juncture. The formation of the cycloadduct **5** could be a direct consequence of the *cis*-ring junction of this lactone which can have a conformational situation 'A' that will bring both the double bonds in close proximity. Studies involving intramolecular alkene cycloaddition to an α,β -unsaturated lactone have previously been restricted to flexible models⁶ with the alkene unit in a side-chain. The present case represents the first case of such a cycloaddition in a rigid system, where conformational situation satisfies the requirement for a cycloaddition. The assignment of structure for the third and remaining material required a very detailed spectral analysis. This was obtained as a solid, m.p. 75–77°. This also had the same molecular formula (C₁₄H₁₈O₄), supported by HRMS. In the $\bar{\nu}$, it showed two strong absorptions at 1780 and 1725 cm⁻¹, attributable to a γ -lactone and ester respectively. ¹H nmr spectra displayed one vinylic methyl group at δ 1.71 as a doublet of doublets, showing a change in the original double bond position. A second methyl group appeared at δ 1.11

Scheme 1

[†] Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

as a doublet revealing its secondary nature, arising from the C-4 methyl in the α,β -unsaturated lactone **3**. Further, the spectrum also showed a broad singlet at δ 4.75 and a multiplet at 5.40 attributable to the angular proton and an olefinic proton respectively. Based on all of above a tentative structure **6** was assigned to the compound which was compatible with all the spectral features. The observed coupling for the vinyl methyl (dd) arises from coupling with the C₆-olefinic proton and further allylic coupling with the C₅-me-

thylene protons which appeared as a multiplet at δ 2.48 also including the C-4 proton. These assignments were further supported by decoupling experiments. Thus, irradiation of the olefinic multiplet at δ 5.45 resulted in the vinylic methyl becoming a triplet, simultaneously reducing the multiplicity at δ 2.48. When the multiplet at δ 2.48 comprising C₄ and C₅ protons was irradiated, the vinyl methyl at δ 1.71 coalesced to a doublet and the secondary methyl at δ 1.11 appeared as a singlet. Finally, irradiation of the vinylic methyl peak at δ 1.71 caused the olefinic multiplet at δ 5.45 to collapse into a triplet. The above observations support the assigned structure **6**. This could be regarded as photo-ene reaction product. A common bi-radical intermediate **7**, resulting from initial interreaction between C₇₋₈ double bond and the α,β -unsaturated lactone moiety could be implicated for the formation of both the cycloadduct **5** and the ene product **6** based on well appreciated mechanistic postulation for photolytic alkene cycloaddition to α,β -enone systems⁷. The formation of the ene product **6** is explicable in terms of a 1,5-hydrogen shift in this biradical intermediate and the configuration of the C-4 secondary methyl group has been assigned from the possible mode of such hydrogen transfer in a six-membered transition state. The predominant formation of photo-ene products during photolysis of compounds containing an alkene and an α,β -enone system has precedent⁸ and has been explained on the basis of stability of the intermediate biradicals. The present case however, constitutes the first example of an intramolecular photo-ene reaction involving an α,β -unsaturated lactone in a rigid system. The cycloadduct **5** and the ene product **6** were obtained in 2 : 3 proportion in a combined yield of 80%. No product arising from cycloaddition of ethylene was traceable in the reaction, confirming that intramolecular reaction takes total precedence in the case of the *cis*-fused lactone **3**. Subsequent photolysis experiments were

carried out in acetone solution. That the products are not inter-convertible photolytically was established from photolysis of the individual compounds which led to only recovery. Similarly, the unsaturated lactone **4** also on photolysis in benzene with added acetone or in acetone as solvent afforded the cycloadduct **8** and the photo-ene product **9** but in 3 : 2 proportion (Scheme 2). The greater proportion of the ene product in case of lactone **3** can be attributed to the stability of the radical in **7** due to presence of the methyl group.

Scheme 2

Although the results on photolysis of the lactones **3** and **4** were at variance with our expectations, this provided some interesting photo-reactions and it became of our interest to explore the chemistry of the novel structures represented by **5** and **6**. To this end the cycloadduct **5** was subjected to basic hydrolysis. Although no unhydrolysed neutral material was obtained even controlled acidification in the cold (below 0°) of the basic solution provided only the cycloadduct **5**, showing spontaneous lactonisation of the generated hydroxy acid. The unsaturated lactone **6** could, however, be easily hydrolysed and the hydroxy acid was esterified with diazomethane to give the hydroxy ester **10** which was oxidised with Jones reagent to furnish the highly functionalised bicyclo(3.2.1)octane derivative **11** (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

In conclusion, we have demonstrated that *cis*-fused hexahydrobenzopyran-2-ones of the type represented by **3** and **4**, on photolysis give rise to novel carbocyclic skeleta arising from intramolecular cycloaddition and photo-ene reaction. The potential of these structures is also illustrated by the transformation of compound **6** to a highly functionalised bicyclo(3.2.1)octane system.

Experimental

Photolysis experiments :

Using bicyclic lactone **3** : A solution of the lactone **3**³ (500 mg, 2 mmol) in dry acetone (150 ml) was irradiated with a Hanovia 450W mercury lamp under N₂ for 8 h. Then

the solvent was evaporated and the residual oil distilled to remove the pinacol formed during the photolysis. The oily residue was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel. Elution with ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (1 : 12) furnished the cycloadduct **5** (130 mg, 30.95%) as an oil, b.p. 120–130°/0.1 mm (Found : C, 67.366; H, 7.67. $C_{14}H_{18}O_4$ calcd. for : C, 67.18; H, 7.25%); ν_{\max} 1780 and 1725 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ 1.20 (6H, s), 1.28 (3H, t, J 7 Hz), 4.23 (3H, q, J 7 Hz), 4.7 (1H, m).

Further elution with ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (1 : 12) furnished the rearranged product **6** (190 mg, 45.2%) as a colourless solid, m.p. 75–77° (petroleum ether, 40–60°); ν_{\max} 1780 and 1725 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ 1.11 (3H, d, J 7.4 Hz), 1.2 (3H, t, J 7.1 Hz), 1.71 (3H, dd, J 3.7, 2 Hz), 2.48 (3H, m), 2.70 (1H, m), 2.88 (1H, m), 4.18 (2H, q, J 7.1 Hz), 4.71 (1H, br s), 55.40 (1H, m.); ^{13}C nmr δ 175.78, 172.12, 132.11, 120.31, 82.227, 60.88, 55.81, 53.03, 50.81, 38.20, 37.82, 21.89, 14.87, 14.18; m/z 250.1197 for $C_{14}H_{18}O_4$.

Subsequent elution with ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (1 : 9) furnished the recovered lactone **3** (80 mg, 16%).

Using bicyclic lactone 4 : A solution of lactone **4** (200 mg, 1.12 mmol) in dry acetone (150 ml) was photolysed as for **3**. The product was subjected to preparative layer chromatography and eluted with ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (1 : 19) and showed three bands. The least polar band afforded the cycloadduct **8** (80 mg, 47%) as an oil, b.p. 120–130°/0.1 mm (Found : C, 73.75; H, 7.88. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2$ calcd. for : C, 74.13; H, 7.92%); ν_{\max} 1770 and 1720 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ 1.14 (3H, s), 1.30 (3H, s), 2.24 (1H, br), 2.9 (1H, m), 3.10 (1H, m), 4.38 (1H, m).

The middle band corresponded to the rearranged product **9** (50 mg, 29.4%), also obtained as an oil, b.p. 120–130°/0.1 mm (Found : C, 73.83; H, 8.26. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2$ calcd. for : C, 74.13, H, 7.92%); ν_{\max} 1770 and 1720 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ 1.22 (3H, s), 1.71 (3H, dd, J 4, 2 Hz), 2.68 (1H, br s), 2.9 (1H, d, J 4 Hz), 4.22 (1H, br s), 5.46 (1H, m). The more polar band was the starting material (30 mg, 15%).

Hydrolysis of lactone 5 : The lactone **5** (60 mg, 0.24 mmol) was added to a solution of KOH (15 mg, 0.26 mmol) in water (1 ml). Enough methanol was then added to make a clear solution and the reaction mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature. The resultant mixture was diluted with water and extracted with ether. Removal of ether afforded no neutral component.

The alkaline aqueous part was acidified in cold (0 to 5°) with dilute H_2SO_4 (10%) and extracted with ether ($\times 2$). The combined ether layers was washed with saturated brine and dried. Removal of solvent, left an oil which was found to be identical with the starting lactone **5**.

Hydrolysis of the unsaturated lactone 6 : The unsaturated lactone **6** (200 mg, 0.8 mmol) was added to a solution of KOH (50 mg, 0.89 mmol) in water (2.5 ml). Enough methanol was then added to make a clear solution and the reaction mixture stirred overnight at room temperature. It was diluted with water and extracted with ether. Removal of solvent left no neutral component.

The alkaline aqueous part was acidified in cold (0°) with dilute H_2SO_4 (10%) and extracted with ether ($\times 2$). The combined ether layers was washed with saturated brine and dried. Removal of the solvent furnished a crude acid which was esterified with diazomethane. The product was subjected to preparative layer chromatography. Elution with ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (1 : 9) furnished the hydroxy ester **10** (180 mg, 90%) as an oil, b.p. 140–150°/0.1 mm; ν_{\max} 3450 and 1725 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ 1.22 (3H, d, J 8 Hz), 1.3 (3H, t, J 6 Hz), 1.7 (3H, s), 2.7 (2H, m), 3.16 (1H, d, J 10 Hz), 3.74 (3H, s), 4.28 (3H, m), 4.5 (1H, d, J 4 Hz), 5.1 (1H, m).

Ethyl-4,7-dimethyl-6-carbomethoxybicyclo(3.2.1)oct-3-en-8-one-carboxylate 11 : The hydroxy ester **10** (40 mg, 0.14 mmol) was taken in acetone (2 ml) and cooled to 0°. To the above stirred solution Jones reagent was added dropwise till a red colour persisted. Stirring was continued for another 1 h. The reaction mixture was then diluted and extracted with ether ($\times 2$). The combined ether layer was washed with aqueous $NaHCO_3$ solution followed by saturated brine and subjected to preparative layer chromatography. Elution with ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (1 : 19) furnished the ketone **11** (30 mg, 71%) as an oil, b.p. 120–130°/0.1 mm; ν_{\max} 1780 and 1725 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ 1.04 (3H, d, J 7.553 Hz), 1.28 (3H, t, J 9.85 Hz), 1.8 (3H, dd, J 5.8, 2.35 Hz), 3.24 (1H, d, J 9.1 Hz), 3.72 (3H, s), 4.32 (2H, m), 5.36 (1H, br s); HRMS calculated mass 280.1311 for $C_{15}H_{20}O_5$, found 280.1305.

References

1. J. R. BAMBERG and F. M. STRONG in "Microbial Toxins", ed. S. KADIS, Academic, New York, 1973, Vol. 3, p. 207; CH. TAMM, *Fortschr-Chem. Org. Naturst.*, 1974, **31**, 64; J. F. GROVE, *Nat. Prod. Rep.*, 1988, 187, and references cited therein.
2. P. G. MCDUGAL and N. R. SCHMUFF, *Prog. Chem. Org. Nat. Prod.*, 1988, **47**, 153; J. D. WHITE, NO-SOO KIM, D. E. HILL and J. A. THOMAS, *Synthesis*, 1998, 619; J. ISHIHARA, R. NONAKA, Y. TERASAWA, R. SHIRAKI, K. YABU, H. KATAOKA, Y. OCHIAI and K. TADANO, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1998, **63**, 2679, and references cited therein.
3. Z. AHMAD, U. K. RAY and R. V. VENKATESWARAN, *Tetrahedron*, 1990, **46**, 957.
4. A portion of this work had appeared in preliminary form : Z. AHMAD, U. K. RAY and R. V. VENKATESWARAN, *Chem. Commun.*, 1990, 708.

5. J. D. WHITE, T. MATSUI and A. J. THOMAS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1981, 46, 3376.
6. B. A. PEARLMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 101, 6398; R. M. COATES, P. D. SENTER and W. R. BAKER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1982, 47, 3597.
7. A. C. WEEDON in "Enone Photochemical Cycloaddition in Organic Synthesis", ed. W. M. HORSPOOL, Plenum Press, New York, 1984, p. 61.
8. R. C. COOKSON, J. HUDEC, S. A. KNIGHT and B. R. D. WHITEOR, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, 19, 1995; G. BUCHI and H. WUEST, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 87, 1589; T. W. GIBSON and W. F. ERMAN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1972, 37, 1148; F. M. SCHELL and P. M. COOK, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1978, 43, 4420.